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**IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MODEL OF FORMATION OF
UNIVERSAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PEDAGOGUES WITH THE
HELP OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES OF EDUCATION AND
TRAINING**

***Abstract.** This article covers background information about the model of universal competence of future pedagogues. In addition to this, the article emphasizes the methods of developing this competence with the help of innovative methods of education and training. Also, the article highlights the main meaning of topic by usage of reliable literature.*

***Keywords.** Gamification, collaboration, project, principle, research, integration, curriculum, reflection.*

It is important for future pedagogues to develop a universal competence that includes skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity. This can be achieved through the use of innovative technologies such as gamification, project-based learning, and online collaboration tools.

Gamification involves the use of game elements in learning activities to make them more engaging and interactive. This can help to develop critical thinking skills by challenging students to solve problems and make decisions in a fun and engaging way.

Project-based learning involves students working on real-world projects that require them to apply their knowledge and skills to solve complex problems. This can help to develop problem-solving skills by providing students with opportunities to work collaboratively, think creatively, and come up with innovative solutions.

Online collaboration tools such as Google Docs, Slack, and Zoom can be used to facilitate communication and collaboration between students and teachers. This can help to develop communication skills, teamwork, and leadership skills that are essential for success in the 21st century.

The universal competence of future pedagogues is to be able to adapt to the changing needs of the education system and the modern world. They must possess a deep understanding of the principles of learning and teaching, as well as the ability to apply innovative approaches and technologies to enhance student learning. They must also be able to work collaboratively with students, parents, colleagues, and other stakeholders to create a supportive learning environment that fosters creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving. In addition, future

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pedagogues must be committed to lifelong learning and professional development to stay up-to-date with the latest research and best practices in education. Ultimately, the universal competence of future pedagogues is to prepare students for success in a rapidly changing world by providing them with the knowledge, skills, and competencies they need to thrive.

- **Adaptability:** The ability to adapt to changing needs of the education system and the modern world.

- **Understanding of Learning and Teaching Principles:** A deep understanding of the principles of learning and teaching.

- **Innovative Approaches and Technologies:** The ability to apply innovative approaches and technologies to enhance student learning.

- **Collaboration:** The ability to work collaboratively with students, parents, colleagues, and other stakeholders to create a supportive learning environment.

- **Creativity:** The ability to foster creativity in students.

- **Critical Thinking:** The ability to foster critical thinking in students.

- **Problem-Solving:** The ability to foster problem-solving skills in students.

- **Lifelong Learning:** A commitment to lifelong learning and professional development.

- **Knowledge of Latest Research:** Staying up-to-date with the latest research and best practices in education.

- **Preparation for Success:** Preparing students for success in a rapidly changing world by providing them with the knowledge, skills, and competencies they need to thrive.

The model of formation of universal competence of future pedagogues with the help of innovative technologies of education and training includes the following stages:

1. **Identification of universal competencies:** The first step is to identify the universal competencies that are required for future pedagogues. These competencies include critical thinking, communication, collaboration, creativity, digital literacy, intercultural competence, and lifelong learning.

2. **Integration of innovative technologies:** The next step is to integrate innovative technologies into the teaching and learning process. This includes the use of digital tools such as online platforms, educational apps, gamification, virtual and augmented reality, and social media.

3. **Development of learning activities:** The third step is to design learning activities that promote the development of universal competencies using innovative technologies. These activities should be interactive, engaging, and relevant to the learners' needs and interests.

4. **Assessment of learning outcomes:** The fourth step is to assess the learning outcomes of the activities using a variety of assessment methods such as formative and summative assessments, peer assessments, self-assessments, and rubrics.

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5. Reflection and feedback: The final step is to provide opportunities for learners to reflect on their learning experiences and receive feedback from their peers and instructors. This helps them to identify their strengths and weaknesses and improve their performance.

The implementation of this model requires a collaborative approach between pedagogues, instructional designers, and technology specialists. It also requires a commitment to continuous improvement and adaptation to changing educational needs and trends. By using innovative technologies to develop universal competencies, future pedagogues can become more effective in their roles as educators and prepare their students for success in the 21st century.

The implementation of the model of formation of universal competence of future pedagogues involves a systematic approach to developing the skills and abilities listed above. This may include:

1. Curriculum Design: Developing a curriculum that emphasizes the development of universal competencies, including cultural competence, emotional intelligence, communication skills, leadership, ethical and professional behavior, flexibility, time management, technology integration, assessment and evaluation, and curriculum development.

2. Instructional Strategies: Using a variety of instructional strategies that promote the development of universal competencies, such as experiential learning, collaborative learning, and reflective practice.

3. Professional Development: Providing ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers to develop their own universal competencies and to learn new instructional strategies for promoting these competencies in their students.

4. Assessment and Evaluation: Developing effective assessment and evaluation strategies to measure the development of universal competencies in students.

5. Collaboration: Encouraging collaboration among teachers, students, parents, and other stakeholders to create a supportive learning environment that promotes the development of universal competencies.

By implementing this model, future pedagogues will be equipped with the skills and abilities needed to create inclusive learning environments that promote educational excellence for all students.

Conclusion, the formation of universal competence of future pedagogues is essential for creating a learning environment that prepares students for success in a rapidly changing world. By using innovative technologies and teaching practices, pedagogues can help to develop the knowledge, skills, and attitudes that are essential for success in the 21st century. By implementing this model, future pedagogues will be better equipped to create inclusive learning environments that promote educational excellence for all students.

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